

whereas for late-maturing ones, the reproductive phase tended to be longer (Table 1).

For the two dominant varieties, Chaloina (early) and Chaae (late), maximum grain yields were measured in fields with no inputs applied but where environmental constraints were minimal. Yields for Chaloina and Chaae reached 308 and 438 g m⁻² at 0% H₂O, respectively (Table 2). These relatively high yields can thus be considered the maximum yield potential in the subsequent analyses of yield buildup processes and agronomic diagnosis of limiting factors and conditions.

Table 2 shows the maximum values of yield components unit area⁻¹ characterizing the classic four successive phases of the yield buildup processes. Threshold values corresponding to the minimum level of the previous yield components required to achieve the potential level of the following one are also provided.

The maximum number of panicles unit area⁻¹ was found to be similar for both varieties but was reached differently. Because of Chaloina's lower maximum number of panicles plant⁻¹, it required a higher threshold of plants m⁻² to achieve a number of panicles (230 m⁻²) similar to the potential achieved by Chaae.

The differentiation in potential yields between Chaloina and Chaae started at spikelet formation and continued in the following phases. A higher maximum number of spikelets panicle⁻¹ was recorded for the late-maturing cultivar as well as a better rate of grain filling (possibly due to more favorable climatic conditions rather than genetic differences) and higher maximum grain weight.

These maxima and the associated threshold values for yield components can be used to construct an empirical model of upland rice yield buildup processes. Such a model can be used for either agronomic diagnoses of limiting factors of yield and for designing and evaluating improved sequences of cultivation practices. ■

Crop resource management

Fertilizer management

Evaluation of P sources in a rice - wheat cropping system in northwestern India

B. Singh, Y. Singh, T.S. Khera, C.S. Khind, and Rachna Nayyar, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, India

Increasing costs have resulted in reduced applications of P fertilizers to rice - wheat systems in the Indo-Gangetic plains of India. Partly to address this issue, nitrophosphate P sources have been developed by acidulation of rock phosphate with nitric acid rather than imported and expensive sulfuric acid. These are cheaper than the traditional superphosphate and diammonium phosphate.

We evaluated three nitrophosphate P sources along with superphosphate and diammonium phosphate on wheat (1996-97) and rice (1997) grown in rotation at Ludhiana in northwestern India. The nitrophosphates contained 80% (Narmadaphos), 60% (ammonium nitrophosphate), and 30% (Suphala) of their total P in water-soluble form. Soil

in the experimental field was a Fatehpur loamy sand with 9% clay, 83% sand, 0.33% organic C, pH 7.4, and 11.2 kg P ha⁻¹ (Olsen P). All P sources were applied to wheat at 17.6, 26.4, and 35.2 kg P ha⁻¹ in a randomized complete block design. No P was applied to rice. Nonetheless, the residual effect of the P sources in the following crop of rice was tested. Both wheat and rice were supplied with 120 kg N ha⁻¹ and 25 kg K ha⁻¹.

The table shows grain yield and P uptake for both rice and wheat. A significant response of wheat to application of P as superphosphate or diammonium phosphate was observed up to 17.6 kg P ha⁻¹. Nitrophosphate fertilizers possessing 60% and 80% P in water-soluble form were as efficient as wholly water-soluble sources in increasing grain yield and P uptake by wheat. The source with only 30% water-soluble P was significantly inferior to other sources even when applied at higher P levels. No residual effect of any of the five sources was observed on the yield and P uptake of rice. ■

Effect of different applied phosphatic fertilizers on grain yield and P uptake by wheat following a crop of rice. Ludhiana, India, 1996-97.

P source	P level (kg ha ⁻¹)	Wheat		Rice	
		Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	P uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	P uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)
No P (control)	0	2.4	7.7	5.2	16.1
Single superphosphate	17.6	3.8	12.3	5.4	17.1
	26.4	4.0	14.1	5.2	16.5
	35.2	4.1	15.9	5.1	15.9
Diammonium phosphate	17.6	4.0	12.9	5.4	16.6
	26.4	4.3	15.1	5.7	17.4
	35.2	4.2	16.0	5.9	17.2
Narmadaphos (80% water-soluble P)	17.6	4.0	13.1	5.2	16.4
	26.4	4.2	15.8	5.6	16.2
	35.2	4.2	15.4	5.8	16.9
Ammonium nitrophosphate (60% water-soluble P)	17.6	4.2	14.2	5.2	16.3
	26.4	4.2	14.8	5.4	15.7
	35.2	4.2	15.4	5.5	16.3
Suphala (30% water-soluble P)	17.6	3.4	12.5	5.0	16.0
	26.4	3.6	13.6	5.7	17.0
	35.2	3.7	13.6	5.2	16.6
LSD (P = 0.05)		0.3	0.7	ns ^a	ns ^a

^ans = not significantly different.